

A Survey on Post-Training Quantization for Vision Transformers

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This survey examines post-training quantization (PTQ) methods for Vision Transformers (ViTs) for low-precision deployment. Our study provides a structured view of the literature through two interrelated taxonomies. The first taxonomy identifies recurring sources of accuracy degradation and deployment difficulty in PTQ of ViTs, referred to in this survey as *Drivers*. It includes depth-wise drift, nonlinear sensitivity in LayerNorm, Softmax, and GELU, coupled attention-path fragility, outliers and heavy-tailed activations, low-bit instability, mixed-precision trade-offs, and deployment limits. The second taxonomy organizes the main Strategy families proposed to address these challenges, including distribution alignment, attention-aware quantization, norm-aware handling, outlier control, reconstruction and rounding optimization, mixed-precision allocation, data-free calibration, and integer-only or kernel-centric redesign. Together, these taxonomies summarize the current state of the art, clarify how different PTQ methods address different sources of accuracy degradation, and provide a structured basis for comparing existing approaches. Beyond taxonomy, the survey links Drivers to the Strategy families that most directly address them, examines existing techniques through evaluation scope, calibration regime, precision setting, and deployability evidence, and summarizes these observations in a practical method-selection guide. Based on this synthesis, we identify several open challenges and future directions, including stronger low-bit stabilization, more practical treatment of LayerNorm and Softmax, improved data-free and mixed-precision workflows, and more consistent deployment-oriented evaluation. By connecting sources of accuracy degradation, mitigation techniques, and practical execution constraints, this survey provides a comprehensive guide for researchers working toward reliable and deployable low-precision ViTs.

CCS Concepts: • **Computing methodologies** → **Computer vision; Neural networks**; *Machine learning algorithms*.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Vision Transformers, post-training quantization, low-precision inference, model compression, mixed-precision quantization, survey

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1 Introduction

Deep learning has become the dominant approach in computer vision, enabling high accuracy on tasks such as image classification, detection, and segmentation [52]. For many years, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) were the standard backbone for vision, with major breakthroughs driven by large-scale datasets and increasingly deep architectures [14, 28, 50]. However, as vision models scaled, it became increasingly important to capture long-range dependencies and global context more directly, motivating attention-based designs in vision [85, 100]. So, Transformers were introduced by [94], and this sequence modeling architecture is built entirely on self-attention, thereby removing recurrence and convolutional operations, enabling highly parallel computation. Vision Transformers (ViTs) adapt this idea to images by representing an image as a sequence of small patches, thereby enabling the Transformer architecture

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53 to be applied to computer vision. After pretraining on large datasets, ViTs can achieve or surpass the top CNN results
54 on many image classification benchmarks [21]. Despite their strong accuracy, ViTs are often costly to run due to their
55 computational and memory demands, making efficient deployment on real hardware an important practical concern.
56 This motivates compression and acceleration techniques that reduce inference cost while preserving accuracy, among
57 which quantization is one of the most widely adopted for practical deployment.

59 Quantization converts a model from full-precision (e.g., FP32) to low-precision (e.g., INT8/INT4) to better match
60 hardware compute and memory constraints during inference. Low precision can reduce the memory footprint and enable
61 faster execution on devices that support efficient integer arithmetic; for example, Jacob et al. propose a quantization
62 approach that enables integer-arithmetic-only inference while maintaining accuracy close to floating-point [38].
63 However, maintaining accuracy is challenging because quantization maps values to a limited set of levels, which
64 introduces quantization error. A key factor is selecting appropriate numeric ranges, since poor range choices can
65 amplify this error. To address this, several methods focus on range and clipping selection; for instance, ACIQ shows
66 that choosing an appropriate clipping range is critical and provides an analytical method to set a clipping threshold
67 that reduces quantization error [3].

71 In Transformers, quantization is often more challenging because activations vary widely across tokens and channels.
72 A few values become much larger than the rest. When this happens, the quantizer must cover a wider range. This
73 reduces precision for most values and can cause a large drop in accuracy [5]. In addition, end-to-end integer inference
74 is difficult because some key operations are very sensitive to low precision. LayerNorm needs mean and variance, and
75 it uses division and the square root. Softmax uses exponentials and division. GELU is a smooth function that is also
76 hard to approximate at low bit widths. For this reason, many quantized Transformers still perform these operations
77 in floating-point. A common yet challenging approach is to replace them with integer-friendly approximations so
78 that the entire model can run in integers. For example, I-BERT approximates LayerNorm, Softmax, and GELU and
79 enables integer-only Transformer inference [47]. These issues are especially important in PTQ, where a pretrained
80 model is converted to low precision after training without updating its weights. In many deployment settings, PTQ is
81 preferred because it avoids retraining costs and can be used when training data or training infrastructure are unavailable.
82 However, PTQ typically relies on a small calibration set to determine quantization ranges and scales, making it more
83 sensitive to outliers and operator-level errors. As a result, PTQ for ViTs needs clear guidance on the main causes of
84 accuracy drop and the methods that address them.

88 This survey reviews PTQ for ViTs and explains why quantizing ViTs after their training remains difficult at low
89 bit widths. We organize the discussion around a Driver-Strategy taxonomy. Drivers are recurring technical reasons
90 for accuracy loss, including attention path interactions, LayerNorm Softmax GELU sensitivity, activation outliers, and
91 depth-wise error accumulation. Strategies are the main families of methods proposed to reduce these errors through
92 better scaling, range control, operator handling, and calibration. Using this structure, we associate each Driver with
93 representative solution strategies and explain when they are most effective across different bit widths and calibration
94 budgets. We conclude with a diagnosis-driven decision guide and a minimal reporting checklist to support reproducible,
95 end-to-end deployment claims.

99 1.1 Comparison with Other Existing Surveys

100 Existing surveys study efficient Transformers and ViTs from broader viewpoints. Tang et al. provide a survey of
101 Transformer model compression spanning both Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Computer Vision (CV), and
102 they organize the literature by compression families such as pruning, quantization, knowledge distillation, and efficient
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Table 1. Contrast with related surveys by taxonomy basis, scope, deployment emphasis, and operator coverage.

Survey	Taxonomy basis	Scope	Deployment emphasis	Operator coverage
Tang <i>et al.</i> [91]	Compression families (pruning, quantization, distillation, efficient design)	Transformers across NLP and CV	General efficiency and compression	Quantization covered, but not centered on ViT PTQ techniques
Chitty-Venkata <i>et al.</i> [10]	Inference optimization across the stack (algorithm → systems/hardware)	Transformers (including ViT)	Systems and accelerator-aware inference	PTQ included as part of inference optimization; not organized by PTQ operator issues
Du <i>et al.</i> [22]	ViT quantization with acceleration / co-design view	ViT low-bit inference methods and hardware acceleration	Algorithm-hardware interplay	Discusses quantization and acceleration considerations beyond PTQ-only framing
Saha & Xu [82]	Edge deployment pipeline (compression + tools + metrics + hardware)	ViTs on edge platforms	Deployment-oriented (HW/SW constraints)	Operators discussed mainly from a deployment and acceleration perspective
Our Survey	Driver-Solution Strategy	ViT PTQ	Deployability evidence (integer-only checks, calibration transparency)	Explicit LN/Softmax/GELU handling + symptom-to-fix mapping

architecture design, rather than centering on ViT PTQ [91]. Chitty-Venkata *et al.* survey Transformer inference optimization across the stack, covering algorithm-level methods, hardware-level techniques, and dedicated accelerators, and briefly discuss PTQ as one component within the broader inference efficiency space [10]. Du *et al.* focus on low-bit ViT inference, reviewing quantization methods alongside hardware acceleration and emphasizing algorithm and hardware interplay rather than a PTQ-focused synthesis [22]. Saha and Xu frame the topic as ViTs on edge, surveying compression, software tools, evaluation metrics, and hardware accelerators for deployment on resource-constrained platforms [82].

In contrast, our survey focuses on PTQ for ViTs because it is the most deployment-friendly quantization setting for modern vision backbones. PTQ converts a pretrained model to low precision after training and does not update the weights, thereby avoiding the high cost of quantization-aware retraining and the need for long training runs. This is important in practice because ViTs are often used as pretrained backbones and must be adapted to new tasks under limited time, compute, or data access. PTQ is also the setting most commonly supported by deployment toolchains, in which a small calibration set is used to establish scales and ranges. At the same time, PTQ for ViTs is technically fragile at low precision. Activation outliers can dominate range selection, and several core operators, especially LayerNorm, Softmax, and GELU, are highly sensitive to low bit widths. As a result, different papers make different design choices regarding which operators to quantize, how to handle these sensitive blocks, how much calibration to use, and whether integer-only execution is achieved. These differences make results hard to compare directly. We therefore organize methods using a Driver-Strategy taxonomy that links why accuracy degrades (Drivers) to how methods mitigate it (Strategies), with explicit attention to LayerNorm Softmax GELU handling and integer-only practicality.

1.2 The Scope of This Survey

This survey examines PTQ for ViTs, with emphasis on the causes of low bit accuracy degradation, the main mitigation strategies, and the practicality of deployment-oriented PTQ pipelines. It covers both classification and downstream tasks, and includes papers in which PTQ is a main contribution. Drawing on literature from 2015 to 2026, Fig. 1 summarizes the paper selection process used in this survey. An initial Google Scholar search using multiple ViT quantization keyword

Fig. 1. Selection process for papers on post-training quantization of Vision Transformers.

families retrieved 900 records, supplemented by few additional papers from venues such as CVPR, ICLR, ICML, ICCV, ICME, and TPAMI. After merging duplicates, 569 unique papers remained. These were screened for relevance to PTQ for ViTs and closely related vision backbones, excluding works outside this scope, as well as QAT-only, survey-only, generic quantization, and hardware-only or compression-only studies. Ultimately, 83 papers progressed to qualitative synthesis and form the basis of this survey.

1.3 Our Taxonomy

Compared to prior surveys, our taxonomy, briefly illustrated in Table 2, reviews the literature on PTQ for ViT by organizing it along three main dimensions:

What causes performance degradation? Drivers: This dimension identifies the main sources that cause accuracy degradation in ViT PTQ under low precision. These include depth-wise drift, nonlinearity sensitivity in components such as Softmax and GELU, coupled attention path fragility, LayerNorm sensitivity, outliers and heavy-tailed distributions, low-bit instability, mixed precision trade-offs, and deployment limits.

What are the mitigation techniques for these drivers? Solution strategies: This dimension groups the main mitigation techniques used to address these accuracy degradation sources. Instead of viewing existing methods as isolated solutions, the taxonomy highlights the common patterns that appear across the literature and shows how they relate to specific sources of quantization difficulty.

Which papers address which driver and strategy combinations? This dimension links each driver to its corresponding solution strategies and representative papers. As a result, the taxonomy not only organizes the literature conceptually but also provides a direct connection from each challenge to the methods proposed to address it.

To keep the taxonomy informative without over-tagging, each paper is assigned a limited number of Driver and Strategy tags, typically one to three in each category. Driver tags capture the main reported or implied causes of low-precision accuracy loss, while Strategy tags capture the principal mitigation techniques most responsible for the

Table 2. Taxonomy of post-training quantization for Vision Transformers, showing major drivers, mapped solution strategies, and representative papers.

Drivers (Sources of Performance Degradation)	Solution Strategies	Representative Papers
D1: Depth-wise drift	S1 + S5	AdaRound [78], QDrop [102], ERQ [119], FIMA-Q [106], APHQ-ViT [107], Bit-Shrinking [67], QEP [1], QwT [26], QwT-v2 [90], iGQ-ViT [77], MROSPU [95], FGPTQ-ViT [33], Bias Compensation [27], MGRQ [114].
D2: Nonlinearity sensitivity (Softmax/GELU)	S2 + S8	PTQ4ViT [117], APQ-ViT [18], MNQ-ViT [44], FQ-ViT [69], IPTQ-ViT [43], AdaLog [105], AIQViT [39], DopQ-ViT [113], ADFQ-ViT [40], TSPTQ-ViT [87], Trio-ViT [84], Q-ViT [60].
D3: Coupled attention-path fragility ($Q/K/V$, QK^T)	S2 + S5	PTQ-ViT [74], APQ-ViT [18], iGQ-ViT [77], OFQ [72], PD-Quant [71], PTQ4ViT [117].
D4: LayerNorm sensitivity	S3 + S8	PracticalEdge [118], RepQ-ViT [66], RepQuant [63], I&S-ViT [120], UniQ-ViT [116].
D5: Outliers and heavy tails	S4 + S1	Outlier-aware Slicing [75], NoisyQuant [73], DopQ-ViT [113], ADFQ-ViT [40], ORQ-ViT [58], Variation-aware ViT Quantization [36], RegCache [48], LRP-QViT [80], Mix-QViT [81], RepQuant [63], QuantTune [8].
D6: Low-bit instability	S5 + S7	QDrop [102], Bit-Shrinking [67], Jumping-through-Local-Minima [25], ERQ [119], FIMA-Q [106], APHQ-ViT [107], QEP [1], I&S-ViT [120], PFCR-ViT [17], PSAQ-ViT v2 [61], DFQ-ViT [93], CLAMP-ViT [79], HC-PTQ [76], MimiQ [11], SARDFQ [121], Eff-DFQT [57], E2H + Activation Correction [92], PSAQ-ViT [64], BiViT [30], BinaryViT [51], BinaryFormer [98], Quantformer [101], TerViT [112], CPT-V [24], Q-HyViT [56].
D7: Mixed-precision trade-offs	S6 + S8	PTQ-ViT [74], LRP-QViT [80], Mix-QViT [81], MPTQ-ViT [88], AMP-ViT [89], LampQ [45], Token-dynamic BW [42], Patch-wise MPQ-ViT [110], PoMQ-ViT [54], P ² -ViT [83], Optimal numerical format [55], MixA-Q [99].
D8: Deployment limits	S8 + S6	PracticalEdge [118], IPTQ-ViT [43], FQ-ViT [69], QwT [26], QwT-v2 [90], P ² -ViT [83], UniQ-ViT [116], AMP-ViT [89], TSPTQ-ViT [87], Trio-ViT [84], Optimal numerical format [55], HC-PTQ [76], H-ViT [70], Domain-Aware PTQ-ViT [97], I-ViT [62], VAQF [86], Auto-ViT-Acc [65], IQGVSA [34], PF2A-ViT [123], HEAT [9], ViTCoD [115], ViTaLiTy [13], Approx. Softmax/LN accelerator [46], N:M sparse transformer accelerator [23], ELSA [35], LRA-QViT [41], PackQViT [19].

reported gains. Multiple tags are allowed when a method addresses several degradation sources or combines multiple components, but priority is given to the dominant technical ideas to preserve readability.

Overall, our taxonomy provides a structured view of the ViT PTQ literature. By linking drivers, solution strategies, and mapped papers, it helps readers understand where quantization errors arise, how existing methods attempt to reduce them, and which parts of the design space have received the most attention. It also helps highlight open directions and offers a clearer basis for future method development, evaluation, and deployment.

Figure 4 makes the taxonomy concrete by placing the Drivers directly on a standard pre-norm ViT block. This operator-level view is useful because PTQ degradation is rarely uniform: in many cases, a small set of operators accounts for most of the accuracy drop. The figure, therefore, helps narrow down where to look first. For example, when the drop appears as soon as attention is quantized, the sensitive points are often the $Q/K/V$ projections, the QK^T logits, and Softmax, where small numeric changes can noticeably alter attention weights. When degradation is more gradual and grows in later layers, it more often points to errors accumulating from residual additions and imperfect scale alignment across blocks. In this way, the map serves as a practical guide: match the observed behavior to a likely Driver, then focus efforts on the operators corresponding to that Driver (e.g., LN/Softmax/GELU handling, outlier control, residual requantization, or block-level reconstruction).

2 Background

2.1 ViT Block Structure and the Need for Model Compression

Figure 2 summarizes the basic structure of a ViT. The input image is divided into fixed-size patches, converted into token embeddings (vector representations of image patches), and processed by stacked Transformer encoder layers. [21] A special [CLS] token (representing the entire image) is often added, and positional embeddings (numerical values that

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Fig. 2. Transformer encoder block (Pre-Layer Normalization) used in ViTs.

encode token order) are included to preserve information about patch order. The token sequence produced by patching and embedding is then passed through a stack of Transformer encoder blocks, which forms the core of ViT processing. Each block has two main parts. First, there is Multi-Head Self-Attention (MHSA), which allows each token to attend to all others and exchange information. Second is the Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), a feed-forward network, refining each token independently using two linear layers with a nonlinearity, commonly GELU. [21, 31] Residual connections (shortcuts that add layer outputs to their inputs) and Layer Normalization (a technique that stabilizes layer outputs) are used around these sub-layers to stabilize the activations as depth increases. This block structure is important for quantization because attention, normalization, and nonlinearities can be sensitive to reduced precision, and errors can accumulate through the residual pathways. [69, 74, 117]

A ViT encoder is a chain of multiple Transformer blocks that operate on a sequence of tokens. Let $X_\ell \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d}$ denote the N tokens (including [CLS]) with embedding dimension d at block ℓ . Each block has multi-head self-attention (MHSA) and an MLP, each with a residual path. Many ViTs use Pre-LN. This means that LayerNorm is applied before each sub-layer, making training more stable in deep models [111]. A typical Pre-LN Transformer block applies LayerNorm before each sub-layer and uses residual connections:

$$\tilde{X}_\ell = \text{LN}(X_\ell), \quad Y_\ell = X_\ell + \text{MSA}(\tilde{X}_\ell), \quad (1)$$

$$\tilde{Y}_\ell = \text{LN}(Y_\ell), \quad X_{\ell+1} = Y_\ell + \text{MLP}(\tilde{Y}_\ell), \quad (2)$$

Layer Normalization also rescales each token vector $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$ using its feature wise mean and variance:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LN}(x) &= \gamma \odot \frac{x - \mu(x)}{\sqrt{\sigma^2(x) + \epsilon}} + \beta, \\ \mu(x) &= \frac{1}{d} \sum_{i=1}^d x_i, \\ \sigma^2(x) &= \frac{1}{d} \sum_{i=1}^d (x_i - \mu(x))^2. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is the input feature vector, d is its dimensionality, $\mu(x)$ and $\sigma^2(x)$ denote the mean and variance of the elements of x , respectively, ϵ is a small positive constant for numerical stability, \odot denotes element-wise multiplication, and $\gamma, \beta \in \mathbb{R}^d$ are learnable affine parameters.

The MLP sub-layer typically expands, then projects back and applies a smooth nonlinearity:

$$\text{MLP}(u) = W_2 \phi(W_1 u), \quad \phi(\cdot) = \text{GELU}(\cdot), \quad (4)$$

where GELU is a standard activation in Transformer feed-forward networks [31].

These operators are also important for quantization: LayerNorm depends on input statistics (mean and variance) and includes a division by the square root of the variance (which can amplify numerical errors), whereas GELU is a nonlinear gate (activation function) whose output can change noticeably under small input perturbations. Moreover, the choice of whether to apply LayerNorm before or after (Pre-LN vs. Post-LN) influences how perturbations propagate through residual pathways across many blocks.

Although ViTs deliver strong accuracy, the next challenge is how to deploy them efficiently. Deploying is challenging when compute, memory, or energy is limited. Each block in ViTs uses large matrix multiplications and intermediate activations in the attention and MLP sub-layers. All these must be read and written repeatedly through memory. As the number of blocks, tokens, and embedding dimensions grows, model size, compute costs, and inference time all increase rapidly. This is a problem for edge or real-time scenarios. Compression helps by reducing inference resources while preserving accuracy. To make ViTs practical, existing approaches prioritize the most expensive parts. One option is pruning, which removes parameters or structural components such as weights, channels, attention heads, or even tokens, thereby reducing computation and memory. However, pruning often leads to irregular sparsity or architectural changes that are not always efficiently supported by hardware, and may require retraining or fine-tuning to recover accuracy. Another option is knowledge distillation, where a smaller student model mimics a larger teacher, trading some training flexibility for a lighter deployment model. While effective, distillation introduces additional training cost and depends on access to the original training data and a well-performing teacher model. A third strategy is low-rank factorization, which approximates large weight matrices with structured low-rank forms to reduce the number of operations. However, this approximation can degrade representational capacity and typically requires careful redesign or retraining of model components. In contrast, PTQ directly reduces numerical precision without modifying the model architecture or requiring full retraining, making it particularly attractive for efficient deployment. Finally, quantization reduces the numerical precision of weights or activations. Quantization is attractive because it cuts memory usage. It can also enable efficient integer-only arithmetic on common hardware, delivering substantial gains in throughput and energy efficiency.

2.2 PTQ: Motivation and Fundamental Concepts

Quantization reduces the cost of neural network inference by representing weights and/or activations using low-bit integer formats (such as 8-bit integers instead of 32-bit floats), enabling smaller models and faster integer arithmetic on common hardware [37, 49]. In practice, quantization is applied either (i) while retraining, i.e., quantization-aware training (QAT), which updates weights for low-precision during training, or (ii) after retraining, i.e., PTQ, which quantizes an already trained network. PTQ is appealing when a strong pre-trained checkpoint is available, but retraining or fine-tuning is too expensive in terms of compute, time, data access, or engineering. Instead of updating model weights, PTQ usually keeps the network fixed. It uses a small calibration dataset, often unlabeled and from the target domain, to estimate activation ranges and statistics for quantization parameters such as scales and zero points. After

365 this lightweight calibration, the quantized model can be exported and deployed. This leads to reduced memory use and
 366 faster, integer-friendly inference [49, 78].
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368 *Affine uniform quantization:* The most common PTQ operator is uniform affine quantization, which maps a real-valued
 369 tensor (multidimensional array) x to an integer tensor q using a scale s and zero-point z :
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$$371 \quad q = \text{clip}\left(\left\lfloor \frac{x}{s} \right\rfloor + z, q_{\min}, q_{\max}\right), \quad (5)$$

$$372 \quad \hat{x} = s(q - z),$$

373 where $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ means rounding-to-nearest and $\text{clip}(\cdot)$ enforces the integer range. In symmetric quantization, z is often set to
 374 0, while s is chosen to match the dynamic range of x .
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378 *Key PTQ design choices:* Given the affine quantizer in (5), PTQ comes down to choosing quantization parameters that
 379 keep rounding and clipping error small. In practice, a small set of design choices has the largest impact.
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381 First, PTQ must set the *range* and *scale*, which determine the range of values the quantizer can represent. A very
 382 wide range avoids clipping large values, but it makes each quantization step larger and increases rounding noise. A
 383 tighter range makes the steps smaller, but it can clip outliers. Methods such as ACIQ [3] aim to select an appropriate
 384 clipping threshold in a principled manner.
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386 Second, PTQ chooses the *scaling granularity*. A single scale for the whole tensor (per tensor) is simple and keeps
 387 metadata small, but it assumes channels have similar value ranges. In practice, channel ranges often differ. A shared scale
 388 can be too coarse for small-magnitude channels, increasing rounding error, and too tight for large-magnitude channels,
 389 increasing clipping. Per-channel weight quantization addresses this by assigning a separate scale to each output channel
 390 and a zero point if needed. This usually reduces quantization error at low bit widths, with modest overhead because it
 391 stores a vector of scales rather than a single value and incurs little runtime cost in common inference implementations.
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393 Third, PTQ decides *calibration* approach. Calibration uses a small set of representative samples to collect activation
 394 statistics and convert them into quantization parameters for inference. Typical statistics include minimum and maximum
 395 values, percentiles, running moments, and histogram-based estimates. Calibration quality often determines PTQ
 396 accuracy, especially at low bit widths where there is little tolerance for mismatch. If the calibration set is too small, not
 397 representative, or the statistic is not suitable, the estimated ranges may be slightly inaccurate. At 4-bit or 2-bit precision,
 398 even small errors can push many values into incorrect quantization levels or increase clipping. These errors can then
 399 propagate through residual paths and attention blocks, leading to a noticeable drop in accuracy.
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403 2.3 From Standard PTQ to ViT PTQ:

404 The standard PTQ choices under the affine quantizer in (5) provide a strong baseline, but ViT PTQ often needs extra
 405 attention. ViTs rely heavily on the self-attention pathway and include operator blocks, especially LayerNorm, Softmax,
 406 and GELU, that are highly sensitive to low precision. As a result, small quantization errors can be amplified across
 407 depth and residual connections, leading to larger accuracy drops, particularly at low bit widths.
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410 *PTQ for CNNs:* For CNNs, a standard method (per-channel weight scaling, reasonable clipping, and a small calibration
 411 set) often delivers strong accuracy. The reason is that CNN building blocks are relatively stable under quantization:
 412 convolution and ReLU are simple, and errors tend to remain local rather than be globally mixed across tokens. When
 413 accuracy still drops at low bit-widths, lightweight reconstruction methods can recover it by aligning quantized outputs
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with floating-point outputs (e.g., AdaRound, BRECQ) [59, 78], and practical guidance is well-established in classic quantization reports [49].

PTQ for ViT. In ViTs, the same PTQ knobs matter more because several components amplify small numerical changes:

- **Attention mixes errors globally.** Quantization noise in the query and key projection outputs, denoted by Q and K , perturbs the attention logits QK^T , and the Softmax can turn small logit changes into noticeable attention redistribution, especially when the logits are close.
- **LayerNorm is statistics-sensitive.** LN depends on mean/variance, low-bit errors can be amplified in low-variance channels, and integer-only LN requires approximations of division and square-root.
- **Nonlinearities and residuals can accumulate bias.** Nonlinear gating (e.g., GELU) and repeated residual additions can accumulate small biased errors with depth [31, 111].
- **Outliers are common.** Token-wise spikes can dominate max-based range selection, wasting quantization levels on rare values and hurting the “typical” tokens; this motivates outlier-aware scaling and reparameterization ideas such as SmoothQuant [108].

ViT PTQ method directions: Most PTQ pipelines for ViTs are built on the standard components of classical PTQ, for example, calibration, clipping, and local reconstruction. They reprioritize it to focus on the Transformer components that are most error-sensitive (attention, LN, nonlinearities, and deep residual accumulation). Modern methods can be broadly grouped into four complementary directions:

(i) **Better calibration and range handling.** Rather than relying on naive min–max ranges, ViT PTQ methods place substantial emphasis on selecting stable activation ranges and scales. This includes principled clipping rules, such as ACIQ [3], which explicitly trade off clipping distortion and quantization noise, and outlier-aware rescaling approaches, such as SmoothQuant [108], which mitigate heavy-tailed activation distributions by shifting part of the quantization difficulty from activations to weights. In practice, these techniques target the observation that a small fraction of large-magnitude values (e.g., in attention/MLP activations) can dominate the dynamic range and degrade low-bit quantization.

(ii) **Reconstruction for Transformer blocks.** Beyond setting scales, many ViT PTQ methods also focus on *reconstructing* quantized behavior to match floating-point outputs. This line extends weight-rounding and reconstruction from layers to more meaningful *Transformer units*: AdaRound and BRECQ optimize rounding decisions using local (layer/block) reconstruction objectives, improving accuracy at lower bit-widths where naive rounding breaks down [59, 78]. For extremely low precision, additional stabilizers, such as QDrop, introduce stochasticity during reconstruction to prevent overfitting to calibration noise and improve robustness in $W2/A2$ -type regimes [102]. The common theme is that *block-aware* reconstruction more effectively captures coupled errors arising from attention, residual additions, and normalization than treating each layer separately.

(iii) **Operator-aware treatment of LN/Softmax/GELU (toward integer-only).** A key deployment obstacle for Transformers is that some operators are numerically sensitive or difficult to implement efficiently in integer arithmetic. As a result, many PTQ pipelines explicitly tailor quantization to LN/Softmax/GELU or replace them with quantization-friendly approximations. Integer-only Transformer inference frameworks, such as I-BERT, provide practical quantized formulations for these operators, thereby reducing reliance on floating-point fallbacks [47]. This operator-aware

469 treatment is particularly important in ViTs because LN depends on token-wise statistics and Softmax shapes attention
 470 distributions, so small numerical errors can propagate nonlinearly through depth.

471 (iv) **ViT-specific PTQ designs targeting attention statistics.** Finally, several methods propose quantization
 472 schemes explicitly designed for ViTs, motivated by the fact that attention and normalization induce distributional be-
 473 haviors that differ from those in CNNs. Representative examples include early PTQ for ViT [74], attention-/nonlinearity-
 474 aware pipelines such as PTQ4ViT [117] and FQ-ViT [69], and later refinements such as APQ-ViT and RepQ-ViT [18, 66].
 475 More recent variants further emphasize efficiency and robustness by explicitly addressing outliers and scaling pathologi-
 476 cles (e.g., P²-ViT, ORQ-ViT) [29, 83]. Conceptually, these approaches modify *where* quantization is applied (e.g., within
 477 attention projections/logits/values) and *how* statistics are handled (e.g., token-/head-wise behavior), because these
 478 choices can matter as much as the quantizer itself.

481 When calibration data are limited or unavailable, **data-free** ideas can also be applied. ZeroQ provides a general route
 482 by synthesizing inputs that match internal statistics without access to the real dataset [7]. At the same time, ViT-specific
 483 data-free approaches take advantage of the Transformer structure to produce richer calibration data (e.g., PSAQ-ViT,
 484 CLAMP-ViT) [61, 79]. Overall, compared to CNN PTQ (often dominated by scale selection plus optional reconstruction),
 485 ViT PTQ typically requires *calibration, reconstruction, and operator/attention awareness together*, because attention, LN,
 486 outliers, and deep residual pathways make error propagation strongly dependent on *where* and *how* quantization is
 487 introduced inside the Transformer block.
 488
 489

493 2.4 Integer-only ViT PTQ: end-to-end deployment pipeline

494 An *integer-only* ViT inference claim refers to a deployment where the full forward pass runs without floating-point
 495 kernels, rather than only quantizing the matrix multiplications in linear layers. This distinction matters because a ViT
 496 block contains several operators that are not simple integer linear algebra. LayerNorm computes mean and variance
 497 and then applies division and square root. Softmax uses exponentials and normalization. GELU applies a smooth
 498 nonlinearity. If these operators are kept in floating point, many runtimes execute them using floating-point kernels and
 499 insert quantize and dequantize conversions around them. These conversions can appear repeatedly inside the block,
 500 which increases overhead and can reduce end-to-end speedups even if the main matrix multiplications are quantized
 501 [38, 47, 62].
 502

504 A common end-to-end flow is summarized in Fig. 3. Starting from a full precision ViT model, a target integer scheme
 505 is selected, for example, W8A8 with INT32 accumulation for dot products. A calibration pass is then run to collect
 506 range statistics at selected tensors in the graph, such as min and max values, percentiles, or histogram based estimates.
 507 These statistics are used to set quantization parameters, mainly scales and optional zero points, for both weights and
 508 activations. The model is then converted into a quantized graph by storing weights in integer form and inserting
 509 activation quantizers at the chosen boundaries so that tensors enter and leave integer representation at defined points.
 510
 511

512 After basic quantization, additional steps are needed to keep the full forward pass in integers. In particular, LayerNorm,
 513 Softmax, and GELU are handled using integer compatible formulations or approximations so that these operators do
 514 not trigger floating-point execution [47, 62]. In addition, residual additions require compatible scaling on both branches,
 515 so implementations often align residual scales or insert controlled requantization before the add. Finally, the quantized
 516 model is exported to the target backend and profiled to confirm that the runtime uses integer kernels throughout and
 517 does not insert floating-point fallbacks.
 518
 519

Fig. 3. End-to-end integer-only ViT PTQ flow

3 Drivers

This section discusses the main sources of accuracy degradation in ViT after PTQ. In this survey, these sources are referred to as *Drivers*. For each Driver, we first point to *where* it shows up in a standard pre-norm ViT encoder block (Fig. 4), and then explain *why* it tends to degrade under low precision.

D1-Depth-wise drift (residual accumulation): D1 arises at the two residual additions in each encoder block: first, when the attention output is added back to the block input, and again when the MLP output is added to the intermediate representation. Each residual add combines a running signal with an update that has been quantized (and often requantized), so small biases can be carried forward. Because the same pattern repeats layer by layer, these small errors can accumulate with depth. Early layers may stay close to FP behavior, while later layers drift as low-precision updates accumulate [1, 63, 66].

D2-Nonlinear sensitivity (Softmax and GELU): D2 appears at the nonlinear operators inside the block: Softmax in the attention block and GELU in the MLP block. These functions can make small numeric changes in the activations more influential on the final output. In attention, Softmax maps logits to attention probabilities, so a small shift in logits can noticeably change how attention is distributed across tokens. In the MLP, GELU controls how strongly each activation is retained or attenuated, so quantization near its transition region can noticeably change the output. For this reason, quantizing or approximating Softmax and GELU can cause a drastic accuracy drop compared with quantizing only linear layers [31, 43, 62, 69].

D3-Coupled attention-path fragility (Q/K/V and QK^T): D3 appears along the attention path that runs through the Q/K/V projections, the QK^T dot-product logits, and the Softmax-weighted combination of V. The key issue is coupling: quantization errors in Q and K affect the logits, and Softmax can translate those logit changes into large shifts in attention weights. This makes attention particularly sensitive to *where* precision is reduced (e.g., projections vs. logits vs. values), and it explains why attention can dominate the overall accuracy drop even when the MLP quantizes reasonably well [69, 74, 77, 117].

D4-LayerNorm sensitivity (normalization boundaries): D4 appears at the LayerNorm boundaries in a pre-norm block, i.e., right before MHSA and right before the MLP. LayerNorm depends on per-token mean and variance and includes a division by $\sqrt{\sigma^2 + \epsilon}$, making it numerically unstable under quantization. Small input changes can shift the estimated statistics, and channels with low variance are particularly sensitive because normalization can amplify relative errors. From a deployment perspective, LayerNorm is also a common point where “integer-only” pipelines break. If LN falls back to floating-point, extra conversions can degrade both speed and numerical consistency [2, 62, 69, 111].

D5-Outliers and heavy tails (range dominated by rare spikes): D5 appears in the tensors that largely determine the quantization ranges within the block: the Q/K/V projection outputs, the attention logits QK^T/\sqrt{d} , the attention output Softmax (QK^T/\sqrt{d})V, and the activations around the two MLP linear layers. In these tensors, distributions are often heavy-tailed so that a few large values can stretch the range. If the scale is set to its maximum, those rare spikes determine the step size, and most values are quantized with low effective resolution. The important point is that outliers indirectly reduce accuracy by forcing coarser quantization on the bulk of values; as a result, most data points lose precision, which in turn drives the drop in accuracy more than the rare outliers themselves [5, 29, 75, 113].

D6-Low-bit instability (brittleness below 6 bits): D6 appears when the model is pushed to very low precision, especially below 6 bits, where the ViT encoder has little numerical margin. In this regime, settings such as W4A4 (4-bit weights and 4-bit activations) become highly sensitive to PTQ design choices, including clipping thresholds, quantization granularity, reconstruction settings, block partitioning, and even the calibration samples used. The main reason is that several precision-sensitive components begin to interact under large quantization noise, including LayerNorm statistics, attention logits and Softmax behavior, GELU in the MLP, and repeated residual additions. As a result, performance becomes more brittle and less reproducible unless the PTQ pipeline is carefully controlled [25, 67, 72, 102, 117].

D7-Mixed-precision trade-offs (whole-architecture precision allocation): D7 sits at the level of the *whole ViT encoder*, because it concerns how bit-width is assigned across operators rather than a single layer. In practice, different parts of the Transformer tolerate low precision very differently: large linear layers (projections and MLP linears) often quantize well, while LayerNorm and Softmax (and sometimes attention logits) are much more sensitive. This creates a system-level trade-off. If we enforce the same low bit-width across the board, accuracy is often limited by the most sensitive operator. If we maintain higher precision at those sensitive points, accuracy can recover, but the runtime benefit may shrink — especially if the backend does not support efficient mixed-precision execution. Many ViT PTQ pipelines, therefore, make an architecture-level decision about which operators can safely run at lower precision and which should remain at higher precision [54, 80, 88, 89, 96].

D8-Deployment limits (operator coverage and conversion overhead): D8 appears at runtime, after the model is exported and mapped to a target backend. Even if accuracy is recovered, speedups depend on whether the backend provides efficient kernels for the full operator set and on how often the runtime must insert quantization/dequantization or requantization steps. In practice, LN/Softmax/GELU and residual scale alignment are frequent bottlenecks. If any of these trigger floating-point fallbacks or conversion-heavy execution, end-to-end latency may improve little (or not at all). Because kernel support and conversion costs vary widely across CPUs, GPUs, and edge accelerators, D8 must be evaluated through end-to-end profiling on the actual deployment stack [62, 70, 86, 97, 118].

4 Strategies

This section discusses the main techniques used to mitigate accuracy degradation in ViT PTQ. In this survey, these techniques are referred to as *Strategies*. We group the literature into eight Strategy families (S1-S8). Each group provides a common approach to improve the accuracy of the ViTs after applying PTQ. Many practical methods combine several families at once. Rather than listing methods one by one, we discuss what each Strategy aims to fix and which design choices affect practical success.

S1-Distribution alignment/correction (calibration, scales, granularity): S1 methods reduce quantization error by making the integer representation match the observed weight and activation distributions. In practice, this comes down to how ranges and scales are chosen (max vs. percentile clipping vs. loss-driven range selection) and how finely the scales are applied (per-tensor, per-channel, per-group, and, in some cases, head-/token-aware variants). Because ViT activations can vary widely across layers and inputs, S1 is often less a single trick and more a calibration protocol; results depend on how representative the calibration data is and how sensitive the chosen rule is to outliers and distribution shifts [3, 38, 40, 66, 77].

S2-Softmax/attention-aware quantization: S2 methods treat the attention path as a special case rather than quantizing it exactly like a stack of linear layers. The motivation is simple: errors in Q/K/V or in the attention logits can alter the Softmax weights, and small shifts in these weights can noticeably change which tokens are emphasized. Common choices include stabilizing or rescaling logits, quantizing attention maps/logits with operator-aware rules, or

625 restructuring attention to reduce sensitivity (including softmax-aware or softmax-free variants). In deployment-oriented
626 settings, S2 additionally provides implementations of the attention probability computation that are amenable to integer
627 arithmetic, thereby mitigating performance bottlenecks that would otherwise arise from using floating-point Softmax
628 [11, 43, 69, 74, 84].

629 **S3-Norm-aware handling (LayerNorm):** S3 methods focus on LayerNorm. LayerNorm is important for accuracy
630 and is also among the hardest operators to run efficiently in low precision. It computes the mean and variance for
631 each token, then normalizes them by dividing by $\sqrt{\sigma^2 + \epsilon}$, so small quantization noise can alter the statistics and
632 the final normalized values. In practice, S3 approaches either keep LayerNorm at higher precision, add LN-aware
633 calibration/correction steps, or use an integer-friendly approximation with careful scaling and ϵ handling. From a
634 deployment perspective, this is also about avoiding overhead. If LN falls back to floating-point or incurs frequent
635 quantize-dequantize steps, the end-to-end speedup can be reduced substantially [2, 43, 46, 62, 69].

636 **S4-Outlier handling and range shaping:** S4 methods address rare but very large values that stretch the quantization
637 range. If the quantization scale is set using the maximum value, a few large spikes can dominate the range, resulting in
638 a larger quantization step size and more coarse representation of most values. As a result, most values get quantized
639 too coarsely. S4 methods adjust the range setting, for example, by using percentile clipping, two ranges (a main and a
640 small-outlier range), or channel grouping to prevent a single spiky channel from affecting all others. A practical concern
641 is deployability. The outlier solution should avoid complex branching or increased data movement; otherwise, speed
642 benefits from quantization may be lost [8, 29, 58, 75, 113].

643 **S5-Reconstruction/rounding optimization:** S5 methods improve low-bit PTQ accuracy for ViTs by explicitly
644 optimizing quantized parameters to more closely match their floating-point counterparts. This often means learning
645 rounding decisions and, sometimes, adjusting scales using a reconstruction objective. Objectives can be applied layer-
646 wise or block-wise. S5 is valuable when calibration alone leaves structured, biased errors that build up through residual
647 paths and operator interactions. There is a trade-off between cost and stability. Results depend on the reconstruction
648 scope (layer vs. block), the iteration budget, and the optimization’s robustness to calibration-subset and random-seed
649 choices [17, 59, 78, 95, 107, 114].

650 **S6-Mixed-precision allocation/search:** S6 methods assign different bit-widths to different parts of the model,
651 based on the fact that some operators tolerate low precision much better than others. Typical pipelines identify sensitive
652 components (via heuristics, sensitivity metrics, or explicit search) and keep them at higher precision, while pushing
653 less-sensitive parts lower under a memory/latency budget. In practice, S6 only pays off when the backend can efficiently
654 execute the chosen precision mix; otherwise, conversion and requantization overhead across precisions can dominate,
655 reducing the net speedup [20, 54, 80, 81, 89, 96].

656 **S7-Data-free synthesis and proxy calibration:** S7 methods are used when real calibration data are unavailable.
657 The idea is to create synthetic inputs (or a proxy dataset) to estimate the ranges and statistics required for PTQ. This is
658 particularly challenging in ViTs, because attention and LayerNorm depend on how tokens relate to each other, not
659 just on simple per-channel averages. For this reason, stronger S7 methods aim to better match meaningful internal
660 behavior (e.g., attention/LN-related statistics) or add additional correction steps to keep the quantized model close to
661 the FP model. When evaluating S7, two practical questions matter: i) do the synthetic samples yield stable quantization
662 parameters? and ii) do the results generalize across different models and datasets rather than relying on a single
663 benchmark [61, 64, 76, 79, 92, 93].

664 **S8-Integer-only/kernel-centric redesign:** S8 methods focus on deployment. The goal is to maintain accuracy after
665 quantization and also achieve real end-to-end speedup on the target hardware. These methods align the quantization
666

Fig. 4. A pre-norm ViT encoder block annotated with Driver regions (D1-D8), highlighting where PTQ-related degradation most often originates

format with what the backend can run efficiently and avoid operators that require floating-point fallback. They often use integer-friendly approximations for LN, Softmax, or GELU, fuse operators where possible, pick packed data formats, and minimize conversions and requantization around residual adds. Different backends support different kernels (CPU, GPU, edge accelerators, or custom accelerators/FPGA flows), so S8 results depend strongly on the runtime. Well-evaluated methods clearly specify the target backend and report end-to-end latency, including evidence that fallbacks and conversion overhead are under control.[9, 34, 62, 70, 86, 118].

5 Driver-Strategy Mapping

This subsection connects each Driver (D1-D8) to a few Strategy families that most directly address it. Some methods are genuinely multi-theme; in those cases, we explicitly assign them to *two Drivers* (still respecting the “ ≤ 2 ” rule) and discuss the relevant contribution under each Driver.

D1 and the main Strategy choices (S1 and S5): D1 is mainly addressed by S1 and S5 because depth-wise drift is driven by two related effects. One is the gradual misalignment between quantized and FP activations across layers, which causes later blocks to operate on increasingly shifted inputs. The other is the local output error left by each quantized layer or block, which is then carried forward through the residual pathway. Under this view, S1 is relevant because it improves the alignment of quantized activations with FP behavior across depth, whereas S5 is relevant because it reduces the local reconstruction error before it can accumulate in deeper layers. Together, these two Strategy families provide a natural pairing for D1.

729 On the S1 side, IGQ-ViT [77] shows that ViT activation statistics can vary noticeably across instances, so a single
730 fixed grouping or scale can introduce a systematic difference between FP and INT activations that later layers inherit.
731 Its instance-aware grouping improves the match between quantized and FP activations, thereby limiting drift across
732 the encoder stack. MROSPU [95] also supports this view by updating quantization scales during low-bit PTQ. In our
733 taxonomy, this can be viewed as a mixed S1 and S5 case, since scale perturbation improves alignment across layers,
734 while reconstruction reduces local block-level error.
735

736 On the S5 side, AdaRound [78] improves rounding so that quantized layer outputs better match FP outputs. QEP [1]
737 makes the D1 interpretation explicit by showing that matching a layer on FP inputs can be misleading when the true
738 inference-time inputs have already been quantized. QDrop [102] improves low-precision reconstruction by incorporating
739 activation quantization during optimization, which increases robustness. ERQ [119] further reduces post-calibration
740 error so that later blocks inherit less mismatch. ViT-focused methods such as FIMA-Q [106] preserve important block
741 outputs more effectively, while APHQ-ViT [107] strengthens MLP-side reconstruction through an average-perturbation
742 Hessian proxy. Bit-Shrinking [67] stabilizes low-bit optimization through a staged schedule, which helps reduce
743 mismatch accumulation. QwT and QwT-v2 [26, 90] further show that lightweight compensation at the block or channel
744 level can reduce persistent post-quantization mismatch under D1 drift. Recent methods such as FGPTQ-ViT [33],
745 MGRQ [114], and bias-compensation-based PTQ [27] further support this interpretation by reducing local output error
746 before it propagates to deeper layers.
747

748 **D2 and the main Strategy choices (S2 and S8):** D2 is mainly addressed by S2 and S8 because nonlinearity sensitivity
749 has both an accuracy and a deployment side. On the accuracy side, Softmax and GELU can make small quantization
750 errors more influential on the final output than in ordinary linear layers. On the deployment side, these same operators
751 are often difficult to execute efficiently in low precision. For this reason, S2 focuses on handling nonlinear-path tensors
752 more carefully so that their quantized behavior stays closer to FP behavior. S8 focuses on making these nonlinear
753 operators practical in a low-precision inference pipeline, especially when integer-only execution is desired.
754

755 On the S2 side, PTQ4ViT [117] shows that post-Softmax and post-GELU tensors are highly non-uniform and
756 therefore require operator-aware treatment to avoid severe accuracy degradation. APQ-ViT [18] further argues that
757 Softmax-related tensors can be heavy-tailed and benefit from quantization that better preserves the resulting attention
758 distribution. Recent PTQ work refines this view in several directions. DopQ-ViT [113] treats PTQ as both distribution-
759 aware and outlier-aware, which is especially relevant when nonlinear imbalance would otherwise amplify quantization
760 error. AdaLog [105] adapts quantization to skewed nonlinear tensors through a log-domain formulation. AIQViT [39]
761 focuses on the sensitivity of post-Softmax representations, where small distortions can alter important attention
762 decisions. ADFQ-ViT [40] also targets nonlinear-path distributions through a distribution-friendly quantization scheme.
763 MNQ-ViT [44] makes this point more explicit by assigning different quantization treatments to different nonlinear
764 functions, acknowledging that Softmax-related and GELU-related tensors should not be handled uniformly. A closely
765 related view is supported by Q-ViT [60], which reinforces the point that accurate low-bit ViT quantization depends on
766 treating nonlinear activations as structurally sensitive tensors rather than as ordinary intermediate features.
767

768 On the S8 side, the same nonlinear operators become a practical deployment bottleneck. Even when their quantized
769 behavior is acceptable in isolation, inefficient handling of Softmax or GELU can force floating-point fallbacks or repeated
770 conversions that reduce the expected runtime gains of low-precision inference. FQ-ViT [69] addresses this issue by
771 proposing a fully quantized ViT pipeline with integer-friendly attention probability computation. IPTQ-ViT [43] is even
772 more direct, since it explicitly quantizes nonlinear functions such as Softmax and GELU to enable integer-only inference
773 without retraining. TSPTQ-ViT [87] introduces a two-scale design to stabilize difficult activations around these operators
774

781 while keeping the computation compatible with fixed-point execution. Trio-ViT [84] approaches the same problem
 782 from another direction by replacing standard Softmax attention with a softmax-free alternative and then building
 783 quantization and acceleration around that simplified operator path. MNQ-ViT [44] also fits this S8 perspective, since
 784 its operator-specific handling is motivated not only by accuracy preservation but also by the need to keep nonlinear
 785 computation practical at low precision. Q-ViT [60] strengthens this deployment-oriented interpretation further, since
 786 its broader goal is to make fully quantized low-bit ViTs practical without leaving nonlinear operators outside the
 787 low-precision inference path.
 788
 789

790 **D3 and the main Strategy choices (S2 and S5):** D3 is mainly addressed by S2 and S5 because attention-path
 791 errors are not confined to a single step. A small perturbation in the query and key matrices, denoted by Q and K , can
 792 change the score matrix QK^\top , which then affects Softmax and alters the resulting attention weights. These altered
 793 weights are subsequently used to aggregate V , so a small error at the start of the path can lead to a much larger change
 794 in the final attention output. This makes the S2 and S5 pairing well-motivated. S2 addresses the problem by treating
 795 attention-related tensors, such as logits, Softmax-related quantities, and attention maps, in an explicitly attention-aware
 796 manner. S5 addresses it by optimizing PTQ settings so that the final attention output remains closer to its FP counterpart
 797 despite the interaction of multiple operators.
 798
 799

800 On the S2 side, PTQ-ViT [74] directly targets the preservation of attention behavior and introduces an attention-
 801 ranking objective to reduce the chance that quantization changes the relative ordering of attention responses. This is a
 802 natural D3 example because instability in attention ordering is one of the main degradation patterns caused by coupling
 803 along the attention path. APQ-ViT [18] follows the same direction but places more emphasis on the Softmax stage,
 804 arguing that Softmax-related tensors exhibit heavy-tailed behavior and therefore require attention-aware treatment to
 805 maintain stable attention computation under quantization noise. IGQ-ViT [77] links the same fragility to statistical
 806 mismatch across inputs. If activation and attention scales vary substantially from one instance to another, a single fixed
 807 grouping or scale can distort logits and attention rows, which then destabilizes downstream attention computation. Its
 808 instance-aware grouping therefore helps reduce mismatch where the coupling is most sensitive. OFQ [72] provides
 809 a complementary perspective. Although studied in a QAT setting, it offers direct analytical evidence that the Q - K
 810 interaction becomes fragile at low precision because the two are interdependent through QK^\top . This supports the D3
 811 view that stabilizing the attention path should be treated as a first-class quantization objective.
 812
 813

814 On the S5 side, the same coupled fragility can be reduced by optimizing PTQ choices against a stronger end objective.
 815 PD-Quant [71] makes this point clearly by tuning quantization parameters through a prediction-difference criterion
 816 rather than relying only on local feature matching. In the context of D3, this is important because attention-path
 817 perturbations may appear small at an intermediate tensor while still producing a meaningful change at the final output.
 818 PTQ4ViT [117] complements this with Hessian-guided sensitivity analysis, which helps identify and calibrate the most
 819 difficult components in the ViT pipeline. Although PTQ4ViT is often discussed under nonlinear sensitivity as well, it
 820 also fits D3 because its stronger sensitivity-aware optimization helps preserve the final attention output when multiple
 821 operators interact through the attention path.
 822
 823

824 **D4 and the main Strategy choices (S3 and S8):** D4 is mainly addressed by S3 and S8 because LayerNorm sensitivity
 825 creates both a numerical problem and a deployment problem. Numerically, LayerNorm depends on per-token mean
 826 and variance estimation, followed by division by $\sqrt{\sigma^2 + \epsilon}$, so even small quantization perturbations can noticeably
 827 affect the normalized output. From a deployment perspective, LayerNorm and its associated scale and shift operations
 828 often make an apparently low-precision ViT pipeline fall back to floating-point execution. This makes the S3 and S8
 829 pairing well-motivated. S3 focuses on keeping the normalized representation stable under quantization, whereas S8
 830
 831
 832

833 focuses on keeping LayerNorm and its surrounding operations compatible with efficient low-precision execution. On
834 the S3 side, RepQ-ViT [66] supports D4 from a statistical viewpoint by observing that post-LayerNorm activations
835 often show severe inter-channel variation. Its scale reparameterization improves quantization quality during calibration
836 while preserving the normalized representation more effectively. RepQuant [63] extends the same intuition to large
837 Transformer models and explicitly identifies LayerNorm, together with Softmax, as an extreme-distribution component
838 that requires specialized handling. This fits D4 well because it shows that LayerNorm sensitivity is not only a local
839 numerical issue, but also part of a broader distribution-mismatch problem under quantization. I&S-ViT [120] similarly
840 treats LayerNorm-adjacent behavior as a major source of instability under PTQ and combines robustness-oriented
841 design choices to reduce drift in normalized activations at low precision. On the S8 side, PracticalEdge [118] is a clear
842 example of the deployment-oriented view. Its goal is not only to quantize the model accurately, but also to preserve an
843 end-to-end integer-oriented execution path. In that setting, LayerNorm becomes a primary issue, since it can otherwise
844 force repeated conversions or floating-point fallback during deployment. UniQ-ViT [116] approaches the same issue
845 from an optimization-oriented PTQ perspective, but it also connects LayerNorm sensitivity to an accelerator-aware
846 view of what must remain stable and executable. This makes it relevant to D4 from the S8 side as well. Taken together,
847 S3 helps preserve the numerical stability of normalized activations, while S8 helps keep LayerNorm practical in a
848 low-precision inference pipeline.

853 **D5 and the main Strategy choices (S4 and S1):** D5 is mainly addressed by S4 and S1 because outliers and heavy
854 tails create two related quantization problems. First, a small number of outliers can dominate the quantization range
855 and force a coarse step size. Second, once the range is distorted in this way, the scale no longer reflects the typical
856 values that make up most of the distribution. This makes the S4 and S1 pairing suitable here. S4 addresses the problem
857 by explicitly controlling, reshaping, or separating the outlier-dominated range so that rare spikes do not determine the
858 quantization scale for the whole tensor. S1 addresses it by refining calibration, grouping, or granularity so that the scale
859 better matches the bulk of the distribution rather than only the extreme tail.

862 On the S4 side, Outlier-aware Slicing [75] is a direct example because it treats outliers as the main source of error and
863 uses slicing so that rare extremes do not dictate the step size for the entire tensor. NoisyQuant [73] addresses the same
864 issue from the activation side by introducing a designed noisy bias together with compensation to reshape heavy-tailed
865 activations and reduce the error caused by tail-dominated scaling. DopQ-ViT [113] is also closely aligned with D5,
866 since it is designed to be both distribution-aware and outlier-aware, arguing that long-tailed distributions and scale
867 mismatch are major causes of quantization degradation in ViTs. ADFQ-ViT [40] similarly fits D5 because it explicitly
868 handles LN-adjacent outliers and distributional imbalance, including difficult post-GELU behavior, through quantization
869 components designed for such distributions. ORQ-ViT [58] makes the D5 especially clear by separating outliers and
870 then quantizing the remaining activations more effectively. Variation-aware ViT Quantization [36] further supports this
871 interpretation by showing that large activation variation and long-tail behavior are persistent sources of degradation
872 in Transformer quantization. Although studied mainly in a QAT setting, its findings still motivate D5-oriented range
873 control in PTQ. QuantTune [8] provides another strong example because it explicitly treats outlier-driven distortion as
874 a major source of quantization error and adapts the correction process around those difficult values.

878 On the S1 side, the same D5 problem can also be reduced by making calibration and scale assignment more represen-
879 tative of typical activations. LRP-QViT [80] uses relevance-based sensitivity to guide mixed-precision assignment and
880 therefore implicitly protects layers or tensors where outliers and range variation are especially harmful at low precision.
881 Mix-QViT [81] follows a similar logic by allocating precision according to layer importance and sensitivity instead
882 of enforcing a uniform low-bit setting when some tensors have much more difficult long-tail statistics than others.

885 RepQuant [63] addresses extreme distributions through reparameterization and range shaping, including LN- and
886 Softmax-related heavy tails, so that tail-dominated scaling is reduced before mapping back to inference-friendly formats.
887 RegCache [48] adds another useful perspective by showing that outliers can also appear as token- or attention-level
888 sinks in vision encoders. By suppressing these dominant components, it reduces the influence of a few extreme values
889 on scale determination and preserves more effective resolution for the remaining activations.
890

891 Taken together, S4 reduces D5 by preventing rare outliers from dominating the quantization range, while S1 reduces
892 D5 by improving how scales are selected and assigned so that the bulk of the distribution retains sufficient effective
893 resolution.
894

895 **D6 and the main Strategy choices (S5 and S7):**

896 D6 is mainly addressed by S5 and S7 because low-bit instability has two closely related causes. First, at very low
897 precision, small reconstruction errors are no longer isolated. They interact through LayerNorm statistics, attention
898 logits and Softmax, GELU behavior, residual scaling, and block-to-block error propagation. Second, this regime becomes
899 highly sensitive to the quality of the calibration signal itself, so weak or unrepresentative calibration inputs can make
900 the final PTQ solution much less stable. This makes the S5 and S7 pairing best suited here. S5 addresses the problem
901 by explicitly optimizing the quantized model so that low-bit error is suppressed more aggressively than in ordinary
902 calibration. S7 addresses it by providing a more stable calibration basis when real data are small, limited, or unavailable.
903

904 On the S5 side, the main idea is to optimize directly for low-bit robustness rather than assume that ordinary
905 calibration will remain reliable. QDrop [102] is a well-known example in this direction. During reconstruction, it
906 accounts for activation quantization and then randomly drops activation quantization during optimization so that the
907 final solution does not overfit to a small and brittle calibration set. Bit-Shrinking [67] addresses the same instability
908 through a staged optimization schedule that limits sharpness and makes extremely low-bit solutions easier to reach.
909 Jumping-through-Local-Minima [25] makes this point even more explicit by treating low-bit quantization as a difficult
910 optimization landscape and using search-like moves to escape poor local solutions. ERQ [119] reduces fragility by
911 directly minimizing quantization error, helping to prevent small early mismatches from being amplified in later blocks
912 under strong quantization noise. FIMA-Q and APHQ-ViT [106, 107] strengthen this reconstruction-oriented line for
913 ViTs by improving how important parts of a block are identified through Fisher-inspired and Hessian-style sensitivity
914 proxies, so that optimization focuses on what matters most at low precision. I&S-ViT [120] also fits naturally here
915 because it is explicitly designed to prevent PTQ from becoming unstable when the target precision becomes extremely
916 low. MGRQ [114] follows the same S5 perspective by using mixed-granularity reconstruction, which improves low-bit
917 robustness by matching different model components with more suitable reconstruction granularity. PFCR-ViT [17]
918 extends this direction with a staged fine-to-coarse reconstruction process that improves optimization stability in
919 ultra-low-bit PTQ. QEP [1] reinforces the D6 interpretation from a depth-wise viewpoint by showing that if upstream
920 quantization error is ignored, low-bit mismatch can grow across depth even when each layer is optimized locally. CPT-
921 V [24] uses a contrastive calibration objective to make low-bit PTQ less fragile, which again reflects the need for stronger
922 optimization objectives once simple calibration is no longer sufficient. Q-HyViT [56] reaches a similar conclusion
923 for hybrid vision transformers, using bridge-block reconstruction to stabilize PTQ under low-bit settings. The same
924 instability is also evident in more extreme low-precision studies such as BiViT [30], BinaryViT [51], BinaryFormer [98],
925 Quantformer [101], and TerViT [112]. Although these works are not always framed as standard PTQ methods, they
926 still provide strong evidence for D6 because they show how quickly transformer accuracy can become unstable once
927 precision is reduced to binary, ternary, or other ultra-low-bit formats.
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937 On the S7 side, the goal is to reduce instability when calibration data are weak, small, or unavailable. PSAQ-ViT [64]
938 is an early example that builds proxy calibration inputs by preserving patch-similarity structure, so the generated
939 activations better resemble those of real ViT inputs. PSAQ-ViT v2 [61] extends this idea with a more accurate proxy-
940 calibration design, again motivated by the fact that low-bit ViT PTQ becomes unreliable when the calibration inputs
941 are poor. DFQ-ViT [93] targets data-free PTQ without fine-tuning and seeks stable quantization parameters even when
942 no real calibration data are available. CLAMP-ViT [79] follows the same direction by combining contrastive data-free
943 learning with adaptive quantization so that synthetic calibration better matches the needs of the quantized model.
944 HC-PTQ [76] represents an even more extreme data-free case, learning quantization parameters and codebooks through
945 clustering without real calibration inputs. MimiQ [11] is another strong S7 example because it uses inter-head attention
946 similarity as a structural guide to generate synthetic data that are more relevant to ViTs under low-bit settings. Data-Free
947 Quantization of Vision Transformers via Semantic Alignment and Reinforcement [121] and Eff-DFQT [57] strengthen
948 this direction further by improving the quality of data-free synthesis and inversion, thereby reducing low-bit fragility
949 when real calibration data cannot be used. Easy-to-Hard Synthesis and Activation Correction [92] also fits naturally
950 here because it progressively improves synthetic calibration quality and then adds activation correction to stabilize
951 quantization in more difficult low-bit regimes.
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956 Taken together, S5 addresses D6 by directly improving reconstruction quality and reducing low-bit error, while S7
957 addresses D6 by supplying a more stable and ViT-relevant calibration basis when real data are limited or unavailable.

958 **D7 and the main Strategy choices (S6 and S8):**

959 D7 is mainly addressed by S6 and S8 because mixed-precision introduces two linked decisions. One is where higher
960 precision should be kept to protect the most sensitive parts of the model. The other is whether the resulting precision
961 plan can still be executed efficiently on the target backend. This makes S6 and S8 a natural pairing here. S6 addresses
962 the first question by allocating bit-widths according to sensitivity. S8 addresses the second by ensuring that the chosen
963 precision and format mix remains practical for deployment.
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966 On the S6 side, PTQ-ViT [74] already motivates this trade-off by analyzing sensitivity in the attention path and
967 using that information to protect fragile components without giving up all efficiency gains. LRP-QViT [80] follows
968 the same principle but uses layer-wise relevance to guide bit-width assignment, so that more important layers are
969 not pushed too low. Mix-QViT [81] reinforces this view by allocating precision according to layer importance and
970 quantization sensitivity, again showing that not all layers should be assigned the same number of bits. MPTQ-ViT [88]
971 makes the allocation process more explicit by introducing a mixed-precision PTQ pipeline that searches or greedily
972 assigns bit-widths under resource constraints, thereby balancing accuracy against compression or latency goals.
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975 AMP-ViT [89] frames the same problem from an efficiency-oriented perspective and packages adaptive mixed-
976 precision PTQ into a workflow that is closer to deployment than to standalone accuracy reporting. LampQ [45]
977 shows that the quality of mixed-precision allocation depends strongly on how sensitivity is measured, and therefore
978 proposes a more structured layer-wise allocation process instead of relying on ad hoc choices. Token-dynamic bit-width
979 assignment [42] pushes this idea to a finer granularity by adapting precision across tokens, reflecting the fact that token
980 statistics and quantization sensitivity can vary substantially across inputs. Patch-wise Mixed-Precision Quantization of
981 Vision Transformer [110] extends this logic to the patch level, demonstrating that sensitivity may also vary within a
982 layer, rather than only across layers. PoMQ-ViT [54] fits the same D7 pattern by combining mixed-precision quantization
983 with Pareto-oriented optimization, so that accuracy and efficiency are balanced jointly rather than optimizing only one
984 of them. MixA-Q [99] further strengthens this direction by revisiting mixed-precision assignment from the activation
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989 sparsity and efficiency point of view, again showing that allocation itself is a major part of the quantization problem
990 rather than a secondary refinement.

991 On the S8 side, the key point is that a mixed-precision plan is useful only if the selected bit-width and format
992 combination can actually run efficiently. A theoretically attractive allocation may still produce little practical speedup if
993 the runtime or backend does not support it well. P²-ViT [83] makes this connection explicit by combining quantization
994 with acceleration through power-of-two scaling and a hardware-friendly execution model, so that the selected precisions
995 and scales map naturally to efficient kernels. Optimal numerical format [55] reaches a similar conclusion from another
996 angle. It shows that once the target precision drops below 8 bits, the number format itself becomes part of the design
997 problem, as the chosen representation must align with backend capabilities to achieve real end-to-end efficiency gains
998 rather than only theoretical compression.

1001 **D8 and the main Strategy choices (S8 and S6):**

1002 D8 is mainly addressed by S8 and S6 because deployment limits arise from two related issues. First, a quantized
1003 ViT may still contain operators or execution paths that do not map well to efficient low-precision kernels. This can
1004 trigger floating-point fallback, repeated quantize and dequantize conversions, or graph-level overheads that reduce the
1005 expected speedup. Second, even when mixed precision is allowed, the selected bit-widths and formats must still match
1006 what the target backend can execute efficiently. This makes S8 and S6 a natural pairing. S8 addresses the problem by
1007 redesigning operators or execution paths so that the quantized model remains practical for low-precision deployment.
1008 S6 addresses it by choosing a precision mix that avoids unsupported operators and conversion-heavy execution paths.

1009 On the S8 side, PracticalEdge [118] is a clear example because it focuses on preserving end-to-end integer-oriented
1010 inference and directly targets the operators that often break low-precision execution on edge backends, especially
1011 normalization and nonlinear components. IPTQ-ViT [43] pursues the same deployment goal from the PTQ side by
1012 quantizing nonlinear functions such as Softmax and GELU after training, which is often the difference between
1013 claimed speedup and realized speedup. FQ-ViT [69] also fits D8 because it explicitly targets a fully quantized ViT
1014 pipeline and introduces integer-friendly attention probability computation so that the nonlinear path does not force
1015 floating-point execution. P²-ViT [83] follows the same deployment-first logic by using power-of-two scaling and
1016 acceleration-aware design choices that reduce scaling and conversion overhead. UniQ-ViT [116] reinforces this view by
1017 combining uniform quantization with outlier and inter-channel-variance suppression, so the resulting model maps
1018 more naturally to hardware-compatible kernels with lower latency. TSPTQ-ViT [87] uses a two-scale design to stabilize
1019 difficult activations while remaining compatible with fixed-point execution. Trio-ViT [84] approaches the same problem
1020 from another direction by removing Softmax through a softmax-free attention design and then building quantization
1021 and acceleration around that structure.

1022 Recent PTQ work supports the same D8 interpretation from a broader systems viewpoint. QwT and QwT-v2 [26, 90]
1023 emphasize that practical PTQ must account for kernel gaps and graph-level overheads, since even small operator-
1024 level mismatches can trigger frequent conversions that erase speedups. H-ViT [70] and I-ViT [62] similarly focus on
1025 hardware-friendly or integer-only ViT inference, again showing that accuracy-preserving PTQ is not sufficient if the
1026 execution path itself remains inefficient. Domain-Aware PTQ-ViT [97] adds another deployment-oriented concern by
1027 showing that inference conditions such as domain mismatch can affect whether a calibrated quantized model remains
1028 practical after deployment. VAQF [86] and Auto-ViT-Acc [65] strengthen the same theme from a co-design perspective,
1029 where quantization decisions are made jointly with accelerator constraints instead of being treated as an isolated
1030 post-processing step.

1041 Work focused more directly on accelerator design reinforces the same S8 view. IOGVSA [34], PF2A-ViT [123],
1042 HEAT [9], and ViTCoD [115] optimize ViT execution paths under integer-only or hybrid-precision assumptions so
1043 that quantization gains are not lost to backend inefficiencies. ViTaLiTy [13] and the approximation-based Softmax and
1044 LayerNorm accelerator in [46] are also relevant because they focus on operators that frequently dominate Transformer
1045 runtime. The N:M sparse Transformer accelerator framework [23] and ELSA [35] make the same point from the sparsity
1046 side, namely that compression helps only when the backend provides a matching execution strategy. LRA-QViT [41]
1047 extends this deployment view by coupling low-rank approximation with quantization for efficient ViT inference, while
1048 PackQViT [19] shows the same principle in a mobile setting, where sub-8-bit quantization becomes practically useful
1049 only when the packing and execution path are designed together.
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1052 On the S6 side, AMP-ViT [89] shows that mixed-precision selection is not only an accuracy tool, but also a deployment
1053 tool. By selecting precision with execution efficiency as an explicit objective, it illustrates how a better precision mix
1054 can avoid unsupported operators, reduce conversion-heavy edges, and keep the graph closer to what the backend can
1055 run efficiently.
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1057 1058 1059 **6 Evaluation Framework and Benchmarking Perspectives** 1060

1061 ViT PTQ results cannot be interpreted reliably through accuracy alone. Similar numerical results may come from
1062 substantially different experimental settings, including different calibration data, different precision targets, different
1063 operator treatments, and different runtime assumptions. As a result, only accuracy values do not fully reveal how
1064 difficult the quantization setting is, how deployable the method is, or how fairly one paper can be compared with
1065 another. For this reason, this section examines the evaluation framework used across the literature.
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1067 To make these distinctions explicit, we frame the discussion around two evaluation dimensions. We begin with
1068 benchmark scope, calibration, and low-bit settings, because the combination of task choice, calibration regime, and
1069 precision target determines how a paper’s evidence should be interpreted. We then consider deployability and runtime
1070 evidence, since practical benefit depends on efficient execution of the quantized model. Finally, we highlight the main
1071 reporting gaps that complicate fair comparison across studies.
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1074 1075 1076 1077 **6.1 Benchmark Scope, Calibration, and Low-Bit Settings** 1078

1079 We first examine the benchmark scope (i.e., the range of tasks, datasets, and metrics used to evaluate a method),
1080 together with calibration and precision settings. These factors determine both the scope of evaluation and the level of
1081 difficulty of the reported ViT PTQ setting. The same bit width can correspond to very different evaluation conditions.
1082 Task choice determines whether the method is tested only on classification or also on downstream tasks such as
1083 detection and segmentation. Calibration choice determines how the quantization parameters are obtained and how
1084 reliable they remain at inference time. Precision choice determines how strongly quantization noise perturbs attention,
1085 MLP activations, and residual propagation. For this reason, papers that report the same bit width are not automatically
1086 comparable. Table 3 summarizes these conditions across benchmark scope, calibration regime, and precision regime,
1087 and shows that similar reported results may still come from different evaluation settings.
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Table 3. Benchmark scope, calibration regimes, and precision settings used in ViT PTQ studies.

Evaluation setting	Few Representative studies	Typical metrics	Interpretation of reported result
Benchmark scope			
Classification Tasks	PTQ4ViT [117], FQ-ViT [69], RepQ-ViT [66], ORQ-ViT [58]	ImageNet top-1 accuracy, sometimes top-5 accuracy	Shows retention of classification accuracy only; it does not by itself establish downstream robustness.
Downstream Tasks	MimiQ [11], FIMA-Q [106], Domain-Aware PTQ-ViT [97], SARDFQ [121]	COCO box AP, mask AP, ADE20K mIoU, Cityscapes mIoU	Shows whether useful representations remain effective on downstream tasks after quantization.
Calibration regime			
Real-data calibration	PTQ4ViT [117], FQ-ViT [69], RepQ-ViT [66], I-ViT [62]	Top-1 accuracy, sometimes accuracy drop from FP	Shows PTQ effectiveness when standard real calibration samples are available.
Reconstruction-based calibration	FIMA-Q [106], APHQ-ViT [107], ERQ [119], PFCR-ViT [17], MGRQ [114]	Top-1 accuracy, low-bit accuracy drop from FP	Shows whether low-bit PTQ remains effective only after stronger reconstruction or post-calibration optimization.
Data-free or proxy calibration	PSAQ-ViT [64], PSAQ-ViT v2 [61], DFQ-ViT [93], CLAMP-ViT [79], MimiQ [11], Eff-DFQT [57]	Top-1 accuracy with synthetic or proxy calibration, sometimes AP or mIoU	Shows whether PTQ remains viable when calibration must rely on synthetic or proxy inputs.
Precision regime			
Standard low-bit PTQ	PTQ4ViT [117], FQ-ViT [69], APHQ-ViT [107], ERQ [119]	W8A8, W6A6, W4A4 top-1 accuracy	Shows behavior in the commonly studied low-bit operating range.
Aggressive low-precision PTQ	OFQ [72], MNQ-ViT [44], BiViT [30], BinaryViT [51], BinaryFormer [98], TerViT [112]	Very low-bit, binary, or ternary accuracy	Shows robustness when precision is pushed into much more severe compression.
Mixed-precision PTQ	LRP-QViT [80], Mix-QViT [81], MPTQ-ViT [88], PoMQ-ViT [54], MixA-Q [99]	Top-1 accuracy, latency, bit-operations, Pareto trade-off points	Shows whether non-uniform bit allocation improves the accuracy–efficiency trade-off.

6.2 Deployability and Runtime Evidence

Benchmark accuracy alone does not show that a quantized ViT is practically useful. A method may preserve strong classification or downstream performance and still fail to deliver real speedups if execution falls back to floating-point, requires frequent precision conversions, or depends on kernels that the target backend does not support efficiently. Good accuracy therefore does not by itself establish deployability.

In ViTs, operators such as LayerNorm, Softmax, and GELU often determine whether low-precision execution remains efficient in practice. If these operators are not handled properly, the gains from quantization can be reduced by floating-point execution and conversion overhead. As a result, papers differ not only in the accuracy they report, but also in the deployment evidence they provide. Table 4 summarizes the main forms of deployability evidence reported in ViT PTQ studies. It groups representative studies by deployment setting, the evidence they report, and the interpretation of a positive result in that setting. This helps distinguish between papers that are accurate under quantization and papers that also demonstrate a viable execution path. Deployability should therefore be interpreted in conjunction with the benchmark, calibration, and precision settings.

Fair cross-paper comparison in ViT PTQ depends not only on the reported result, but also on how fully the evaluation setting is described. Although quantized accuracy is usually reported clearly, calibration size, operator handling, backend assumptions, and runtime setup are often presented less consistently. This makes it harder to determine whether two methods were evaluated under comparable conditions, especially when they differ in calibration source, precision setting, or execution path. For this reason, fair comparison of PTQ results depends on the full evaluation setting along with the reported accuracy.

Table 4. Deployability and runtime evidence reported in ViT PTQ studies.

Deployment setting	Few Representative studies	Typical evidence	Interpretation of reported result
Integer-oriented operator handling	PracticalEdge [118], IPTQ-ViT [43], FQ-ViT [69], I-ViT [62]	Integer-only inference claims, operator treatment for Softmax, GELU, and LayerNorm, accuracy with full low-precision execution	Shows whether sensitive nonlinear and normalization operators can be executed without falling back to floating-point.
Runtime-aware PTQ design	QwT [26], QwT-v2 [90], H-ViT [70], Domain-Aware PTQ-ViT [97]	Latency, speedup, graph-level overhead, backend compatibility, runtime-aware calibration or compensation	Shows whether PTQ remains effective once conversion overhead, unsupported kernels, and real inference conditions are taken into account.
Mixed-precision for deployability	AMP-ViT [89], P ² -ViT [83], Optimal numerical format [55], PackQViT [19]	Latency, throughput, number-format choice, packing efficiency, hardware-friendly scaling	Shows whether the chosen precision and number format can be translated into an efficient execution path rather than only an accurate one.
Hardware and accelerator co-design	VAQF [86], Auto-ViT-Acc [65], HEAT [9], ViTCoD [115], PF2A-ViT [123]	Hardware utilization, throughput, accelerator-aware quantization, kernel support, co-designed execution path	Shows whether quantization choices remain useful when hardware constraints and accelerator support are treated as part of the design problem.
Structured execution support	ViTaLiTy [13], Approx. Softmax/LN accelerator [46], N:M sparse transformer accelerator [23], ELSA [35], LRA-QViT [41]	Operator approximation, sparsity-aware execution, low-rank support, hardware-matched compression strategy	Shows whether compression or approximation leads to runtime benefit only when the backend provides a matching execution strategy.

7 Practical Method Selection Guide for ViT PTQ

This section presents a simple workflow for selecting a ViT PTQ pipeline from the Strategy families (S1 to S8). Fig. 5 is the starting point. First, practical constraints such as access to calibration data, integer-only deployment requirements, backend support, and target bit width are used to select an initial route. Then, if accuracy drops or deployment is not clean, we add one relevant Strategy family and test again. This keeps the process clear and avoids unnecessary trial and error. For convenience, this section uses coarse calibration-effort labels to indicate the approximate amount of post-training optimization required by a method. **C0** denotes statistics-only calibration without iterative optimization, as in calibration-based PTQ methods that set scales from activation ranges or percentiles [38, 49]. **C1** denotes light iterative tuning with a limited optimization budget, such as learning rounding decisions or performing layer-wise reconstruction with a small number of optimization steps, as in AdaRound and QDrop [78, 102]. **C2** denotes heavier reconstruction-based or second-order optimization, as in methods such as BRECCQ and GPTQ [33, 59].

7.1 Workflow for selecting a PTQ route

Begin at the start node in Fig. 5. For each question, select the matching branch and continue.

Define constraints: First, note the target bitwidth, the backend or runtime, the calibration budget, and the task. These choices determine what can be deployed in practice and how much tuning is feasible.

Check calibration data access: The tree first checks whether you have real calibration images from the target domain or a close match. If not, follow route **R6**. In **R6**, use **S7** (data-free, proxy) to generate proxy inputs and collect the

Fig. 5. Decision tree for selecting a ViT PTQ pipeline under practical constraints. First, decide on data access and whether integer-only end-to-end execution is required. If no real calibration data are available, use R6 (S7 + S1). If integer-only execution is required, use R5 (S8 + S1) with fallback and quantize/dequantize (Q/DQ) audit. Otherwise, choose the bitwidth route R1-R4. Dashed arrows indicate that bitwidth is selected after proxy calibration (R6) or backend feasibility checks (R5).

statistics needed for quantization. Then apply **S1** (calib, scales) to set ranges, scales, and granularity from the proxy samples. If you also need integer-only execution, apply **S8** (integer-only, kernels) and verify that the graph does not fall back to floating point. After proxy calibration, continue to the target bitwidth node, since you still need to choose the deployment bitwidth.

Check whether integer-only execution is required: If real calibration data are available, the next question is whether integer-only end-to-end execution is required. If yes, follow route **R5**. In **R5**, start with **S8** (integer-only, kernels) and also use **S1** (calib, scales) to set quantization parameters from the calibration data. Define how LayerNorm, Softmax, and GELU are handled on the target runtime. Then, validate the exported graph for floating-point fallback and for quantization and dequantization boundaries. After this backend check, select the target bit width supported by the backend. Report runtime evidence on the target backend, since accuracy alone does not confirm deployability.

Choose the bitwidth route: If integer-only execution is not required, choose the target bitwidth and start from the matching route:

- **R1 (W8A8):** Start with **S1** (calib, scales). If LayerNorm is sensitive, add **S3** (LayerNorm). This route often fits low calibration effort (C0 to C1).
- **R2 (W6A6):** Start with **S1** + **S3**. If the attention or Softmax path is the main source of error, add **S2** (attn, Softmax). If outliers dominate the ranges, add **S4** (outliers, range). This route is usually C1.
- **R3 (W4A4 or W4Ax):** Start with **S5** + **S1**. At 4 bits, reconstruction or rounding optimization is often needed because calibration alone can leave structured errors. If needed, add **S2**, **S3**, or **S4** based on what fails. This route is usually C1 to C2.

- **R4 (3 bit or below):** Start with strong **S5**. If your policy and backend allow it, use **S6** (mixed precision) for the most sensitive operators. This route is usually C2. Report the seed and the sensitivity of the calibration subset, since very low bitwidth runs can be unstable.

7.2 Debugging and Reporting Deployable PTQ

Fig. 5 suggests a practical way to respond when PTQ accuracy drops or when deployment fails. The figure includes links from **R5** and **R6** back to bitwidth selection, because bitwidth is still chosen in these cases. A simple troubleshooting workflow is to start from the selected route, add one Strategy family, and test again. This keeps the debugging process clear and avoids mixing many changes at once. If LayerNorm is the main source of error, add **S3** (LayerNorm). This can include LayerNorm-aware calibration, keeping LayerNorm at higher precision when allowed, or using an integer-friendly approximation when integer-only execution is required. If the attention or Softmax path is sensitive, add **S2** (attn, Softmax). Typical fixes include attention-aware quantization, logit stabilization, and integer-friendly Softmax variants for deployment. If outliers dominate the ranges and a small number of large values set the scale, add **S4** (outliers, range). Common choices are clipping rules, range shaping, or grouping methods that reduce the impact of rare spikes. If deeper blocks degrade more than early blocks, strengthen **S5** (recon, rounding). In practice, this often means block-level reconstruction, a larger optimization budget, and checks for calibration-subset and random-seed sensitivity. If the deployed graph includes floating-point fallback operators or many quantize and dequantize boundaries, strengthen **S8** (integer-only, kernels). This is primarily a deployability issue and usually requires kernel-compatible operator choices, fusions, and careful control of conversions.

For deployment-focused PTQ claims, it is recommended to report a minimum set of evidence so results are verifiable on real runtimes. First, state a clear operator policy for LayerNorm, Softmax, and GELU, such as quantized, approximate, mixed-precision, or fallback. Next, report a fallback and boundary audit. List any floating-point fallback operators. Also report the number and locations of quantization and dequantization boundaries, particularly around LayerNorm, Softmax, and residual paths. Then provide backend details, including the runtime or library, version, hardware, and any kernel or operator limits that affect feasibility. Include runtime evidence such as end-to-end latency or throughput, or profiler output on the stated backend. Finally, report the calibration budget as C0, C1, or C2 and the calibration set size. If an optimization method is used, report the number of iterations or steps. For W4 and below, also report seed or subset sensitivity. If **S7** (data free) is used, report the synthesis objective and budget, and add evidence that proxy calibration produces stable quantization parameters.

Deployability claims are most convincing when accuracy and runtime benefits hold in full application pipelines, not only on ImageNet classification. In the surveyed literature, ImageNet remains the most common evaluation setting and is typically reported using top-1 accuracy [14]. When downstream tasks are reported, object detection is the most frequent, followed by segmentation. Most detection and instance segmentation results use MS COCO and report COCO-style Average Precision (AP), including AP, AP50, and AP75 [68]. For semantic segmentation, ADE20K and Cityscapes are common benchmarks, and results are typically reported using mean Intersection over Union (mIoU) [12, 122]. These application-level results provide useful evidence that some PTQ choices can generalize beyond classification, but comparisons remain challenging because task pipelines differ across papers in operator targets, calibration setups, post-processing, and the metrics reported. For this reason, deployment-oriented PTQ studies benefit from reporting at least one downstream task setting alongside ImageNet, using standard datasets and metrics, and clearly stating the scope of quantized operators and runtime conditions.

Fig. 6. Roadmap of PTQ for ViTs: The timeline shows the progression from early foundations in model compression and quantization to transformer architectures and the emergence of ViT PTQ. Recent trends highlight component-aware PTQ, improved low-bit robustness, MP strategies, and deployment-aware design.

8 Summary and Challenges

In this section, we first revisit the evolution of PTQ for ViT, from general compression and quantization foundations to recent ViT PTQ developments, and then highlight the limitations of current methods and the remaining challenges.

8.1 Trends and Status Quo

Figure 6 presents a concise roadmap illustrating how research on efficient neural network inference has progressed from early model compression techniques to recent PTQ methods designed specifically for ViT. Three major phases can be observed in this evolution.

The **first phase** focuses on developing foundational model compression techniques. Early research explored pruning to reduce network complexity, followed by broader formulations of model compression and parameter redundancy. Subsequent work investigated low-rank approximations, knowledge distillation, and structured sparsity to further improve computational efficiency and deployment feasibility. During the same period, quantization emerged as an important direction for reducing the computational and memory requirements of deep neural networks. Quantization-aware training became a strong baseline for preserving model accuracy, while PTQ attracted increasing attention due to its ability to quantize models without retraining. Hardware-aware and mixed-precision quantization later extended this line of work by incorporating deployment constraints and bit allocation strategies into the quantization process [4, 6, 15, 16, 20, 32, 38, 53, 96, 103].

The **second phase** begins with the introduction of the Transformer architecture and its later adaptation to computer vision through the Vision Transformer. Once Vision Transformers demonstrated strong performance in image recognition tasks, research attention quickly shifted toward improving their inference efficiency. However, the architectural characteristics of transformers, such as attention techniques, LayerNorm operations, and nonlinear activations such

1353 as Softmax and GELU, pose new challenges for conventional quantization methods. As a result, methods originally
1354 designed for convolutional networks could not be directly applied to Vision Transformers without significant accuracy
1355 degradation [21, 94].
1356

1357 The **third phase** corresponds to the emergence of dedicated PTQ methods for Vision Transformers. The first
1358 specialized approach appeared in 2021 and established a starting point for this research direction [74]. Subsequent work
1359 quickly moved toward transformer-aware designs that explicitly address sensitivity in attention modules, normalization
1360 layers, and nonlinear activation functions. Later studies focused on improving accuracy under low-bit settings through
1361 better scale handling and reparameterization strategies. More recent approaches increasingly incorporate mixed-
1362 precision assignment, hardware-aware optimization, and adaptive quantization techniques, reflecting a broader shift
1363 from purely accuracy-oriented objectives toward practical deployment considerations [66, 69, 88, 89, 117].
1364

1365 Overall, this roadmap highlights a clear transition from general compression and quantization techniques toward
1366 specialized PTQ strategies tailored to Vision Transformers. Current research increasingly emphasizes low-bit robustness,
1367 mixed-precision design, and deployment efficiency, suggesting that future progress will depend not only on improving
1368 quantization algorithms but also on aligning them with practical system constraints.
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1371 8.2 Challenges

1372 There are practical gaps between reported ViT PTQ results and deployable inference, and these issues remain important
1373 for reliable end-to-end deployment.
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- 1376 • **Deployability gap beyond quantized accuracy** A major challenge is the gap between quantized accuracy
1377 reported in papers and the behavior of the same model on real execution backends. Many studies report
1378 quantized weights and activations, but do not verify whether the executed graph remains integer only on the
1379 target runtime. In practice, several operators inside a ViT block are difficult to support efficiently in low precision.
1380 LN, Softmax, and GELU often trigger floating-point kernels or introduce repeated quantize and dequantize
1381 boundaries. Residual paths may require additional scaling and requantization before element-wise additions.
1382 When these conversions recur across blocks, the overhead can offset the gains obtained from quantized matrix
1383 multiplications, which reduces end-to-end speedups even when the reported accuracy is strong [38, 47, 62].
1384 Only a subset of the ViT PTQ literature explicitly targets integer-only viability or reports backend-level
1385 deployment evidence, including FQ ViT, I ViT, PracticalEdge, IPTQ ViT, P² ViT, and Trio ViT [43, 62, 69, 83,
1386 84, 118]. In general, practical deployment evidence is strongest when papers report operator coverage, end to
1387 end latency or throughput on a specified backend, and the cost of conversions, requantization, and fallback
1388 operators. Without these details, it is difficult to determine whether a method improves practical deployment or
1389 only improves offline accuracy.
1390
- 1391 • **Execution stack dependence** Deployment conclusions depend strongly on the execution stack, including
1392 hardware, runtime, kernel libraries, and graph-level optimizations such as fusion. In the taxonomy, this depen-
1393 dence is reflected by deployment constraints and deployment-aware redesign, but its practical meaning differs
1394 across platforms [83, 104, 109, 118]. A method can appear highly effective on one platform and only moderately
1395 useful on another because the dominant bottleneck changes across hardware classes, even when the quantized
1396 model itself is unchanged.
1397

1400 On CPUs, INT8 SIMD matrix multiplications can be efficient, but conversion and requantization overhead may
1401 dominate the runtime. On GPUs, low-precision matrix multiplications offer high throughput, yet LN, Softmax,
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and GELU are often best supported in FP16 or BF16, which encourages MP execution. On edge NPUs and ASICs, efficiency depends on supported numeric formats, operator sets, and static graph rules. On FPGAs, results depend heavily on HW and SW co-design choices and on the toolchain, which makes direct comparison with SW-only deployments less straightforward.

- **Low bit degradation in fragile operator paths** The surveyed literature indicates that low-bit degradation is often concentrated in a small number of numerically fragile components rather than being distributed uniformly across the network. As precision decreases, the LN and Softmax path and the nonlinear MLP path containing GELU become dominant sources of error. These same operators also remain major barriers to integer-only execution. LN is sensitive because it depends on accurate variance estimation and normalization. Softmax is sensitive because exponentials and normalization can amplify small logit errors. GELU is difficult because its nonlinear shape is hard to approximate accurately at very low precision. Errors in these components can propagate through residual paths and attention mixing, which further amplifies degradation over depth. Because of this, many ViT PTQ methods emphasize operator-aware handling, including scale redesign around residual additions, stabilization of attention logits and Softmax, and integer-friendly formulations of normalization and nonlinearities [43, 62, 69, 84, 87]. However, technical reporting in very low precision settings is often incomplete. Important details, such as fixed-point formats, accumulator precision, approximation error bounds, and explicit accuracy-efficiency trade-offs, are not always specified, even though they can strongly affect both correctness and runtime.
- **Calibration cost, stability, and comparability** Another challenge is that strong low-bit accuracy recovery often depends on reconstruction-based optimization, whose cost and stability vary significantly across methods. Approaches such as AdaRound, BRECO, QDrop, ERQ, FIMA Q, and APHQ ViT can substantially reduce quantization error by optimizing rounding decisions or reconstructing layer and block outputs [59, 78, 102, 106, 107, 119]. While effective, their outcomes depend on calibration size, optimization budget, and sometimes random seeds. This becomes more pronounced for W4A4 and below, where small differences in calibration data or optimization settings can lead to noticeable changes in final accuracy. These factors also reduce comparability across papers. Reported results often depend on pretrained checkpoints, preprocessing pipelines, calibration subsets, and runtime assumptions. In low bit settings, these differences can dominate the apparent gains attributed to the quantization method itself. Data-free PTQ adds further variability because proxy data quality strongly affects both numerical stability and realism [7, 61, 64, 76, 79, 93]. Overall, the field still lacks sufficiently consistent reporting of calibration size, calibration procedure, optimization budgets, stability, and runtime settings.

9 Conclusion

This survey presented a structured review of PTQ for ViTs, focusing on the technical factors that make low-precision deployment difficult and the practical conditions required for reliable inference. By organizing the literature through a Driver-Strategy taxonomy, the survey clarified both why accuracy degradation under quantization occurs in ViTs and how existing methods attempt to address it. In this way, the paper moves beyond isolated accuracy comparisons and provides a more systematic view of the PTQ design space for ViTs.

The survey shows that PTQ for ViTs should not be viewed as a single accuracy-recovery problem. Rather, it is a combined problem of accuracy degradation diagnosis, low-bit stabilization, and deployable execution. ViTs remain difficult to quantize because attention computations are tightly coupled, operators such as LayerNorm, Softmax, and

GELU are highly sensitive to reduced precision, and activation statistics can vary significantly across tokens and channels. As a result, PTQ results must be interpreted together with benchmark scope, calibration regime, target precision, operator handling, and deployability evidence, rather than through reported accuracy alone.

A key contribution of this survey is that it connects recurring accuracy degradation drivers with the main strategy proposed in the literature, and extends that structure into practical guidance. This view suggests that effective PTQ methods typically target the dominant source of degradation, rather than relying on generic quantization heuristics. It also shows that strong low-bit results often depend on stabilization techniques such as reconstruction, improved rounding, outlier-aware handling, mixed precision, or operator redesign. At the same time, fair comparison across studies requires transparent reporting of calibration effort, optimization budget, stability, operator coverage, and runtime or backend evidence. Overall, the current literature suggests that meaningful progress in PTQ for ViTs depends on balancing three closely related objectives: preserving accuracy, maintaining stability under aggressive precision reduction, and achieving genuinely hardware-efficient inference. From a practical perspective, the survey further translates the taxonomy into a method-selection workflow that helps researchers choose an initial PTQ route based on deployment constraints, target bitwidth, calibration access, and backend support, while the reporting checklist highlights the evidence needed to make deployment claims credible and reproducible. Future work should therefore focus on more deployable low-precision formulations of LayerNorm and Softmax, stronger treatment of coupled Transformer behavior in low-bit settings, clearer efficiency-aware handling of outliers and mixed precision, more reliable data-free and low-calibration PTQ, and more standardized evaluation and reporting practice. By combining taxonomy, evaluation guidance, and practical selection principles, this survey aims to serve as both a conceptual reference and a useful foundation for developing more accurate, transparent, and deployment-ready PTQ methods for ViTs.

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